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Research Article

SURGICAL COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the surgical complications of diabetes mellitus.

Patients and Methods: The case series covered the fifty cases of diabetes mellitus and each case is studied elaborate history was taken; thorough general physical examination was done along with meticulous examination of the local lesions. Relevant lab investigations were carried out as depicted in the proforma. Each patient was treated according to the respective problems. Severe foot infections, spreading cellulitis, osteomyelitis of the bone, and gangrene of the toes and the feet were subjected to surgical treatment. Minor amputations like toe amputation, disarticulation of the toes was done for gangrene of the toes. In case of gangrene with spreading cellulitis of foot, fore foot amputation was done. In severe cases of infections and gangrene spreading to the foot and to the leg, major amputations like below knee / above knee or hip disarticulation was done. The frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.

Results: During six months study period total fifty diabetic patients were explored for surgical complications. The frequency for male and female population was 30 (60%) and 20 (40%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 52.65 ± 7.84 and 54.96 ± 5.84 respectively. Regarding the type of surgical complication septic lesion 30 (60%), neuropathies 08 (16%) and ischemia 12 (24%) while among septic lesion the ulcer 08 (26.6%), gangrene 07 (23.3%), abscess 06 (20.0%), carbuncles 02 (6.6%), cellulitis 07 (23.3%) and among bacteriology staphylococcus aureus 10 (33.3%), pseudomonas 07 (23.3%), e. coli 03 (10.0%), klebsiella 04 (13.3%), others 06 (20.0%) whereas regarding the treatment modalities, conservative 16 (32%), incision draining / excision 10 (20%), disarticulation 08 (16%), transmetatarsal amputation 06 (12%), below knee amputation 07 (14%) and above knee amputation 03 (6.0%).

Conclusion: Surgical complications are more prevalent in diabetic population.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Surgery complication, Diabetic foot and Amputation.

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INTRODUCTION:

In prior ages previously insulin was found patients were kicking the bucket because of careful difficulties of diabetes like carbuncle, abscesses, ulcers, and gangrene [1]. Presently because of accessibility of insulin in purged frames, wide range anti-microbials and refined careful procedures these inconveniences are handled effectively [2]. So it is beneficial to find out about these complexities of diabetes that required careful intercession [3]. A broad research about careful difficulty of diabetes is finished. These investigations are made as patients with diabetes are having a more extended life than before. So they live into the age bunches where the careful confusions are seen every now and again [4]. Contaminations of the foot and gangrene of the foot in diabetics have a high occurrence. So it is important to examine them in detail. Safe anesthesia, liquid and electrolytes the board, great anti-microbials and right agent methods have helped specialists to manage these inconveniences securely and proficiently [5]. Apart from cataracts the major surgical complications are septic lesions includes Furuncles, abscesses, carbuncles, cellulitis, foot infections and neuropathic lesions which includes acute neuropathy, chronic neuropathy, autonomous neuropathy and diabetic acropathy and ischaemic lesions which includes vascular insufficiency of the limbs, ischaemic ulcers and gangrene [6].

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The case series covered the fifty cases of diabetes mellitus and each case is studied elaborate history was taken; thorough general physical examination was done along with meticulous examination of the local lesions. Relevant lab investigations were carried out as depicted in the proforma. Each patient was treated according to the respective problems. Generally, all the patients admitted for surgical complications were first made to get fasting blood glucose. Broad spectrum antibiotics were initiated. In case of ischaemic lesions vasodilators and

pentoxifylline were started. Antiplatelet drugs once daily were initiated to improve local blood circulation. In patients with septic lesions like abscess, furuncles, and carbuncles incision drainage, excision was done either under local anaesthesia or under general anesthesia. Pus was taken for culture and sensitivity. Ulcers were treated a thorough debridement which included slough excision was done. Dirty ulcers were also treated with hydrogen peroxide solution to help in separating the slough. Clean ulcers were dressed with povidone iodine solution preparations. Ulcers with healthy granulation tissue which were ready for grafting were dressed with wet saline dressings.

Severe foot infections, spreading cellulitis, osteomyelitis of the bone, and gangrene of the toes and the feet were subjected to surgical treatment. Minor amputations like toe amputation, disarticulation of the toes was done for gangrene of the toes. In case of gangrene with spreading cellulitis of foot, fore foot amputation was done. In severe cases of infections and gangrene spreading to the foot and to the leg, major amputations like below knee / above knee or hip disarticulation was done. At the time of discharge counseling was given regarding foot care, preventions of ulcer. Patient was asked to follow up regularly for residual ulcers. The data of all patients was required on pre-designed proforma while analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the qualitative and quantitative variables.

RESULTS:

During six months study period total fifty diabetic patients were explored for surgical complications. The frequency for male and female population was 30 (60%) and 20 (40%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 52.65 ± 7.84 and 54.96 ± 5.84 respectively. The demographical and clinical profile of study population and the management modalities are presented in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY (N=50)	PERCENTAGE (%)
AGE (yrs)		
30-39	10	20
40-49	14	28
50-59	14	28
60+	12	24
GENDER		
Male	30	60
Female	20	40
TYPE OF SURGICAL COMPLICATION		
Septic lesion	30	60
Neuropathies	08	16
Ischemia	12	24
SEPTIC LESION		
Ulcer	08	26.6
Gangrene	07	23.3
Abscess	06	20.0
Carbuncles	02	6.6
Cellulitis	07	23.3
BACTERIOLOGY		
Staphylococcus aureus	10	33.3
Pseudomonas	07	23.3
E. coli	03	10.0
Klebsiella	04	13.3
Others	06	20.0

TABLE 2: TREATMENT MODALITIES OF STUDY POPULATION

TREATMENT	FREQUENCY (N=50)	PERCENTAGE (%)
Conservative	16	32
Incision draining / excision	10	20
Disarticulation	08	16
Transmetatarsal amputation	06	12
Below knee amputation	07	14
Above knee amputation	03	6.0

DISCUSSION:

In current series lower limbs followed by upper limbs, back were affected sites. Commonest surgical complications of diabetes in this study are septic lesion, followed by ischaemic lesions and neuropathic lesions. In present study the majority of septic lesions yielded staphylococcus aureus and then pseudomonas followed by E.coli, Klebsiella and proteus. Pus and culture sensitivity was done and most of the organisms were resistant to ampicillin, gentamycin, penicillin while the mild sensitivity to ciprofloxacin, moderately sensitive to cephalosporins. Regarding neuropathies, the Patients gave history of parasthesia, hyperaesthesia, tingling numbness and weakness of the feet. On examination, trophic changes of the toes, absent sweating, absent sense of fine touch, vibration, pain, sensory modalities was seen. Peripheral neuropathy is a noteworthy reason for foot injuries because of diabetic microangiopathy, vasanervosa of the digital nerves are included bringing about demyelination [7]. Hence forth diminished cutaneous sensation, proprioception, pain perception and joint sense [8]. It additionally influences the engine filaments bringing about decay of natural muscles and loss of curves of the foot. Autonomic fibers are involved resulting in loss of sweating and temperature regulation. Due to all these features trivial injury are left unnoticed which get infected and cause non healing tropic ulcers [9]. Gangrene and amputation are commonly observed in patients with uncontrolled diabetes [10] and in present study the common surgical intervention included incision draining / excision disarticulation, transmetatarsal amputation, below knee amputation and above knee amputation respectively.

CONCLUSION:

Surgical complications are more prevalent in diabetic population with male gender predominance and lower limbs are most commonly involved followed by upper limbs while the septic lesions are common complications followed by ischaemic lesions and neuropathic lesions. When lesions failed to respond

to conservative treatment or spreading gangrene the major amputations is the treatment option.

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